

Factors Influencing the Success of Mobile Phone Entrepreneurs at Central Plaza

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Abstract—The purpose of this research was to study the factors that influenced the success of mobile phone entrepreneurs at Central Plaza. The sample group included 187 entrepreneurs at Central Plaza. A questionnaire was utilized as a tool to collect data. Statistics used in this research included frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Independent- sample t- test, one way ANOVA, and multiple regression analysis. Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The findings disclosed that the majority of respondents were male between 25-40 years old, and held an undergraduate degree. The average income of respondents was between 15,001-25,000 baht. The majority of respondents had less than 5 years of working experience.

In terms of personality, the findings revealed that expression and agreement were ranked at the highest level. Whereas, emotion stability, consciousness, open to new experience were ranked at high. From the hypotheses testing, the findings revealed that different genders had different success in their mobile phone business with different income from the last 6 months. However, difference in age, income, level of education, and experience affected the success in terms of income, number of customers, and overall success of business. Moreover, the factors of personalities included expression, agreement, emotion stability, consciousness, open to new experience, and competitive strategy. From the findings, these factors were able to predict mobile phone business success at 66.9 percent.

Keywords—Entrepreneur, Influencing Factors, Success, Mobile Phone Business.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS, a mobile or cell phone is one of the most important factors in our daily life. This is because the mobile phone is not just a mean of communication but it is a connection with a lot of human activities such as entertainment, knowledge, fashion and status. For the decade, mobile phone business is not only a growing and thriving, but also spinning off other business opportunities [1].

The thriving business of the mobile phone has created a lot of jobs as well as business. To be successful in any business can make an individual feel more worthy and proud according to Maslow theory (1960) who believed that human beings processed a set of motivation system and people are motivated to achieve ascertain needs; therefore, a good job is one of the best human motivators [2]. However, whenever a person has the opportunity to do a preferred work, it does not guarantee the success of the job. This means there are many factors of success. If one knows the factors that may contribute more to

the success of each job or each occupation, one can embark the job with more confidence.

The mobile phone business in Thailand is in a very competitive business. There is an oversupply of mobile phone stands and retailers in most of the shopping areas. The mobile phone business entrepreneurs should therefore understand the characteristics of success such as motivation, confidence, ability to manage and plan and other key factors of success [3].

Mobile mart zone is formed by many small mobile phone entrepreneurs at Central Plaza and the management of Central Plaza has agreed to allow this special area for the convenience of customers. Since there are many mobile phone retailers concentrated in a limited area, the competition becomes very severe. Central Plaza has decided to expand the zone since there is also a huge demand and the zone has become a success [4].

From the literature review, the researcher expected that personality and strategy to compete should influence the success of the mobile phone entrepreneurs. In this study, the focus was to understand the factors that influence the success. The findings could therefore be used to create a strategic marketing plan to increase customer satisfaction.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. The Objectives of This Research

1. To compare the success of the mobile phone business according to the demographic information of entrepreneurs.
2. To study personality and strategy to compete which influences the success of the mobile phone entrepreneurs.

B. Research Hypotheses

Based on literature survey the following hypotheses have been derived:

1. Difference demographics of the entrepreneurs have different success in mobile business.
2. Personality and strategy to compete of the entrepreneurs has an influence to the success in mobile business.

C. Research Framework

The research framework used in this paper is based on the theory of personality [5] and the concept of strategy to compete [6]; this is the strategy to make the difference, strategy to quick response, strategy to focus, and concept of success [7].

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Fig. 1 Conceptual framework

The population of this study included all the mobile phone entrepreneurs at Central Plaza in Mobile Mart zone which had approximately 350 mobile phone retailers from 7 branches of Central Plaza all over Bangkok area, Thailand. The sample used in this research was collected from 187 mobile phone retailers by using two stages sampling techniques. First stage, the proportional stratified random sampling technique was utilized to get the representative sample from each branch of Central Plaza around Bangkok area. Second stage, the random sampling technique was utilized by drawing the number of each mobile phone retailer and process to ask the respondent to answer the questionnaire.

III. FINDINGS

The findings revealed that the majority of mobile phone entrepreneurs were male between 25 - 40 years old, with an undergraduate degree. The average income of the respondents was 10,001- 15,000 baht per month. The average experience in the field of phone business was about 5 years. In terms of personality, the majority of respondents had personality of expression, agreement in the highest level and personality of emotion stability, conscious, and open to new experience in the high level. They also had the strategy to compete as well as the success of business in the high level.

From the hypotheses, the findings revealed that different gender of mobile phone entrepreneurs had a different success in term of income. Also differences in terms of age, income, level of education, and experience of mobile phone entrepreneurs had different success in terms of income, rate of customer increase, and the success of business.

For the income increase of mobile phone entrepreneurs, the findings revealed that their income increase had been influenced by the seven variables. The seven variables and its correlation coefficient could be reported as follows. The seven variables were strategy to make a difference, emotion stability, open to new experience, conscious, strategy to focus, expression, and agreement. The correlation coefficient

included 0.497, 0.435, 0.530, 0.419, 0.598, 0.379, and 0.395 respectively.

For the rate of customer increase for mobile phone entrepreneurs, the findings revealed that the rate of customer increase had been influenced by the six variables. The six variables were emotion stability, conscious, strategy to make a difference, agreement, expression, and strategy to focus. The correlation coefficient included 0.579, 0.323, 0.503, 0.668, 0.471, and 0.217 respectively.

For the business success for mobile phone entrepreneurs, the findings revealed that the business success had been influenced by the six variables. The six variables were strategy to make a difference, emotion stability, strategy to focus, quick response, and open to new experience. The correlation coefficient included 0.518, 0.394, 0.306, 0.676, 0.515, and 0.206 respectively.

For the overall rate of business success for mobile phone entrepreneurs, the findings revealed that the overall business success had been influenced by the seven variables. The seven variables were strategy to make a difference, conscious, open to new experience, agreement, expression, strategy to focus, and emotion stability. The correlation coefficient included 0.346, 0.128, 0.319, 0.303, 0.245, 0.207 and 0.186 respectively.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Differences in gender of mobile phone entrepreneurs had a difference success in term of income. The result of this study concurred with the work of Kamchai who studied the factor of success of insurance sale representatives and found that difference in gender had different success in terms of income [8]. From the findings, males tended to be more success in terms of income than females, this may happen because mobile phone business was very competitive and male entrepreneurs were more aggressive than female entrepreneurs.
2. Difference in age of mobile phone entrepreneurs had difference in overall success. The result of this study concurred with the findings of Chukajohn who studied factors of success of insurance sales representative and found that age made the different in terms of success for overall business [9]. Old sales representative with more experience tend to be more successful.
3. Difference in income of mobile phone entrepreneurs had a difference in overall success. The result of this study agreed with the findings of Pantywa who studied factors of success of employees and found that income made the different in terms of success in the overall business [10]. The reason behind this finding may come from the fact that whenever the entrepreneur makes more money, they tend to invest more and expand their business success.
4. Different in level of education of mobile phone entrepreneurs had difference in overall success. The result of this study agreed with the findings of Nititanachot who studied factors of success of car salesman and found that the level of education made the difference in terms of success in the overall business [11]. The reason behind

this finding may come from the fact that whenever an entrepreneur who has a higher education, they will utilize their knowledge for business and tend to make less mistakes.

5. Different in level of experience of mobile phone entrepreneurs had a difference in overall success. The result of this study concurred with the findings of Kamchai who studied the factor of success insurance sale representatives and found that the level of experience made the different in terms of success in the overall business [12]. The reason behind this finding may come from the fact that whenever an entrepreneur who has a higher experience, they tend to learn from their mistake and past experiences and finally tend to make fewer mistakes.
6. The variables that influenced the success of the mobile phone business in terms of income success were strategy to compete and strategy to focus. This result also concurred with the findings from the study of Kamchai who explained that the entrepreneur who did not have any strategy plan often had less business success. On the other hand, the variable that influenced the success of the mobile phone business in terms of rate of customer increase were the variables of agreement and this also concurred with the findings from the study of Kamchai [12].

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V. RECOMMENDATION

The findings revealed that the strategy to compete and the strategy to focus had a very high correlation coefficient. Therefore, they were important variables to influence the success of mobile phone business. In addition, personality in terms of agreement and consciousness had a very high correlation coefficient. This means the mobile phone entrepreneurs should focus on these variables in a practical way such as the mobile phone suited for a specific market, has a variety of mobile phone accessories, try to use personality techniques of being friendly and agreeing with customers when they make any purchase decision. Be patient and be polite to customers who may need more details of description and explanation.

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